

Synthesis of monoesters monochlorides and γ -ketoesters

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Abstract : In the present work previously prepared monoesters (**1-20**) on treatment with thionyl chloride have been converted to monoacids monochlorides (**1a-20a**). The monoacids monochlorides thus obtained were treated with diethyl cadmium bromide to afford corresponding γ -ketoesters (**1b-20b**) in yields good. The products were purified by column chromatography and characterized by spectroscopic techniques like, UV, NMR 1D and 2D (¹H and ¹³C), IR and Mass measurements.

Keywords : Monoesters monochlorides, benzyl alcohols, γ -ketoesters.

Introduction

Gamma ketoesters are very useful bifunctional intermediates and have been used in the synthesis of important compounds and flavors¹⁻³. Many methods of their synthesis have been reported in the literature⁴⁻¹¹. Some of these methods require expensive catalysts and/or reactions conditions that are not easily manageable^{5,12}. Moreover, almost all known examples of synthesized γ -ketoesters vary in the ketoacid part of the esters but not in alcohol part⁴⁻¹². Very few report about examples different in alcohol moiety of the esters indicate that a little work has been done in this respect^{13,14}. In this regard synthesis of γ -ketoesters from succinic anhydride involving three step reaction strategy has enjoyed much interest in the synthetic organic chemistry¹⁵⁻¹⁷. This inspired us to undertake synthesis of γ -ketoesters with different alcohol part. Present study describes the synthesis of mono-, and di-substituted benzyl γ -keto hexanoates (**1-20**) obtained from previously prepared monoesters^{13,14}.

Results and discussion

Characterization of **1a** :

The preparation of compounds **1a-20a** and **1b-20b** is displayed in Scheme 1. Compounds **1a** and **1b** are representative of the two series and their structure characteri-

R = mono- or di-substituted benzyl group

Scheme 1. Preparation of **1a-20a** and **1b-20b**.

zation has been discussed in detail. The compound **1a** was obtained as viscous oil in 78% yield (1.91 g). Its HR-MS spectrum indicated [M⁺] at *m/z* 295.54 corresponding to molecular formula C₁₁H₉Cl₃O₃. Its UV spectrum in ethanol absorbed at λ_{max} 257.9 nm (log ϵ 3.7). The main difference in the IR spectra of **1** and **1a** was the absence of OH peak for the initial monoester **1**. Three aromatic protons (Ar-H, 3H) displayed in the IR spectra a peak at 3086. Two peaks at 1721 and 1777 cm⁻¹ in the IR spectra of **1a** were assigned to ester (C=O) and acid chloride (1777, Cl-C=O), respectively. IR spectrum **1a** showed peaks for double bonds of benzyl ring at 1610, 1478 cm⁻¹ (C=C). Ether linkage was confirmed by the presence of bands at 1262, 1144, 1021 cm⁻¹ (C-O). The C-Cl bond formation was evident from a peak at 720 cm⁻¹, indicating the formation of C-Cl bond.

Formation of **1a** was verified by ¹H NMR and ¹³C NMR (Tables 1 and 2). In the ¹³C NMR spectra, a peak at δ 176.3 was indicative Cl-C=O bond. In its ¹H NMR

Table 1. ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3 , δ , multiplicity, J in Hz) of **1a-20a**

Compd.	3	2	1''	Ar-H	R	R'
1a	2.91, t, 6.8 Hz	2.67, t, 6.8 Hz	5.06, s	7.18–7.87, m, 3H		
2a	2.90, t, 6.8 Hz	2.71, t, 6.8 Hz	5.05, s	7.32–7.74, m, 3H		
3a	2.92, t, 6.8 Hz	2.68, t, 6.8 Hz	5.07, s	7.46–7.66, m, 3H		
4a	2.93, t, 6.8 Hz	2.69, t, 6.8 Hz	5.18, s	7.25–7.77, m, 3H		
5a	2.91, t, 6.8 Hz	2.68, t, 6.8 Hz	5.22, s	7.41–7.79, m, 3H		
6a	2.92, t, 6.8 Hz	2.69, t, 6.8 Hz	5.06, s	7.05–7.22, m, 3H		
7a	2.93, t, 6.8 Hz	2.68, t, 6.8 Hz	5.07, s	6.58–7.46, m, 3H		
8a	2.91, t, 6.8 Hz	2.70, t, 6.8 Hz	5.07, s	6.76–7.24, m, 3H		
9a	2.92, t, 6.8 Hz	2.71, t, 6.8 Hz	5.11, s	7.22–7.83, m, 3H		
10a	2.90, t, 6.8 Hz	2.68, t, 6.8 Hz	5.04, s	6.88–7.22, m, 3H	2.38, s, 3H (Me)	2.38, s, 3H (Me)
11a	2.92, t, 6.8 Hz	2.69, t, 6.8 Hz	5.05, s	6.98–7.19, m, 3H	2.39, s, 3H (Me)	2.39, s, 3H (Me)
12a	2.92, t, 6.5 Hz	2.77, t, 6.5 Hz	5.11, s	7.22–7.27, m, 4H	2.35, s	
13a	2.92, t, 6.5 Hz	2.76, t, 6.5 Hz	5.21, s	7.13–7.52, m, 4H	2.36, s	
14a	2.96, t, 6.5 Hz	2.81, t, 6.5 Hz	5.21, s	7.15–7.21, m, 4H	2.37, s	
15a	2.87, t, 6.5 Hz	2.74, t, 6.5 Hz	5.24, s	6.78–7.32, m, 4H	13.41, br, s	
16a	2.92, t, 6.5 Hz	2.75, t, 6.5 Hz	5.22, s	6.93–7.36, m, 4H	13.24, br, s	
17a	2.93, t, 6.5 Hz	2.77, t, 6.5 Hz	5.23, s	6.88–7.15, m, 4H	12.78, br, s	
18a	2.90, t, 6.5 Hz	2.69, t, 6.5 Hz	5.10, s	6.87–7.32, m, 4H	12.32, br, s	
19a	2.91, t, 6.5 Hz	2.70, t, 6.5 Hz	5.12, s	6.82–7.31, m, 4H	12.33, br, s	
20a	2.92, t, 6.5 Hz	2.71, t, 6.5 Hz	5.18, s	6.76–7.27, m, 4H	12.31, br, s	

Table 2. ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl_3 , δ) of **1a-20a**

Compd.	4	3	2	1	1''	1'	2'	3'	4'	5'	6'	R	R'
1a	176.3	38.5	28.4	168.2	62.8	138.2	132.3	131.4	133.2	126.3	128.5		
2a	175.9	38.7	28.8	168.7	62.9	138.8	127.6	129.3	128.5	131.6	127.8		
3a	175.8	38.4	28.6	169.4	57.5	142.5	134.5	128.3	130.6	28.3	134.5		
4a	175.7	38.4	28.8	169.2	66.2	138.3	129.4	133.7	133.7	131.6	128.4		
5a	175.6	38.6	28.7	169.6	66.3	145.0	126.5	136.7	129.4	136.7	126.5		
6a	174.7	37.9	28.3	170.2	62.3	130.4	138.8	148.3	115.4	125.6	123.6		
7a	174.3	37.5	28.6	170.4	62.5	122.5	162.4	105.8	162.7	113.4	132.6		
8a	173.9	37.6	28.9	170.3	61.8	130.8	156.4	116.7	115.6	159.5	114.7		
9a	174.5	38.3	28.1	170.5	54.9	115.7	160.5	112.4	129.7	112.4	160.5		
10a	175.6	38.0	28.4	169.9	65.4	138.6	136.7	132.1	136.7	125.6	125.9	20.6	22.4
11a	174.7	37.8	28.2	170.4	65.8	141.2	130.1	129.0	126.7	134.5	127.8	19.3	22.8
12a	175.2	37.5	28.9	168.9	66.3	140.8	132.3	122.5	122.3	124.2	129.4	20.6	
13a	174.2	37.4	28.3	168.9	66.4	135.3	128.2	137.8	128.2	126.9	125.4	22.5	
14a	174.9	37.1	28.2	168.8	66.1	136.4	127.6	128.5	136.4	128.5	127.6	22.4	
15a	174.8	37.5	28.1	168.7	63.2	127.8	154.3	115.2	127.8	122.7	131.3		
16a	174.7	38.1	28.5	168.8	66.3	136.4	113.2	158.3	116.1	131.4	120.2		
17a	175.3	37.4	28.5	168.6	66.2	127.8	130.2	115.8	156.5	115.8	130.2		
18a	174.9	38.2	28.4	168.7	63.5	142.4	115.6	127.3	125.2	126.3	138.8		
19a	174.7	37.9	28.8	168.8	65.9	136.5	115.3	145.4	114.6	128.5	118.4		
20a	175.1	37.6	28.2	168.3	66.1	125.6	128.5	114.4	146.6	114.4	128.5		

spectra compound **1a** displayed four peaks due to four different groups of protons. Peaks at δ 2.91 (t, J 6.8 Hz) and 2.67 (t, J 6.8 Hz) were attributed to two methylene groups. A singlet at δ 5.06 was due to CH_2O group. In ^{13}C NMR **1a** revealed eleven peaks for eleven different carbons (Table 2). The peaks at δ 138.2, 132.3, 131.4, 133.2, 126.3 and 128.5 were for aromatic carbons. Two peaks at δ 38.5 and 28.4 were due to two methylene groups between ester and acid chloride. The assignment was also verified by HMBC spectrum, in which the proton resonating at δ 2.67, displayed interactions with carbon resonating at δ 176.3, was attributed to COCl . In the high resolution electron impact HR-EIMS spectrum, **1a** displayed a molecular ion peak at (295.55), Calcd. for $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_9\text{Cl}_3\text{O}_3$ (295.55) : C, 44.70; H, 3.07; Cl, 35.99; Found : C, 44.68; H, 3.11; Cl 35.88%. The structure of the remaining compounds (**2a-20a**) was established in the same way.

Characterization of **1b** :

Our γ -ketoesters differ from those previously reported, mainly in the nature of alcohol part of the ketoesters. The alcohol part of the esters is mono- or di-substituted benzyl group. The substituents include electron releasing as well as electron withdrawing. The carbon atoms in monoesters acid chlorides (**1a-20a**) and ketoesters (**1b-20b**) are numbered for spectral data assignment (Fig. 1).

R and R' are substituent at 2, 3, 4, 5 or 6 position
Benzene ring is mono- or di-substituted
Y = Cl = **1a-20a**; Y = Et = **1b-20b**

Fig. 1. Atom numbering in compounds for assignment of spectral data.

Compound **1b** was obtained as viscous oil (yield 78%, 1.91 g). Its HR-EIMS showed molecular ion (M^+) peak at m/z 289.15 with relative intensity 33%. It exhibited UV-Vis absorption band in ethanol solvent at λ_{max} 258.5 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 3.72) and was assigned to aromatic chromophore.

The compound **1b** in IR displayed bands at 3076 (Ar-H), 1728 (CO_2Ar), 1767 ($\text{C}=\text{O}$), 1615, 1479 ($\text{C}=\text{C}$), 1267, 1148, 1023 ($\text{C}-\text{O}$), 722 ($\text{C}-\text{Cl}$) cm^{-1} . The assignments are compatible with the structure of **1b**. Two additional peaks than **1a** at 1.05 (t, J 7.4 Hz), 2.46 (q, J 7.4 Hz) and corresponding peaks in ^{13}C NMR at 7.8 and 36.3 were assigned to newly introduced ethyl group (Tables 3 and 4). Two triplets in the ^1H NMR (Table 3) of **1b** at δ 2.46 (q, J 7.4 Hz) and 2.91 (t, J 6.8 Hz) were assigned to two methylenes. A low field singlet at δ 5.06 was assigned to CH_2O protons. In the ^{13}C NMR spectra (Table 4) of **1b**, the other assignments are; δ 209.4 (C-4, $\text{C}=\text{O}$ of ketone), δ 32.3 (C-3, CH_2), δ 29.1 (C-2, CH_2), δ 171.8 (C-1, $\text{C}=\text{O}$ of ester), δ 62.9 (C-1'', CH_2O), δ 137.5 (C-1'), δ 131.2 (C-2'), δ 129.3 (C-3'), δ 133.6 (C-4'), δ 126.8 (C-5') and δ 128.6 (C-6'). Finally the structure of **1b** was also confirmed by analytical data that led to the calculation of molecular formula $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{14}\text{Cl}_2\text{O}_3$ (289.15) : Calcd. C, 54.00; H, 4.88; Cl, 24.52; Found : C, 54.05; H, 4.89; Cl, 24.51%. Formation **1b** was also confirmed by 2D NMR techniques (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Presentation of 2D NMR in **1b**.

Table 3. ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3 , δ , multiplicity, J in Hz) of **1b-20b**

Compd.	6	5	3	2	1''	Ar-H	R	R''
1b	1.05, t, 7.4 Hz	2.46, q, 7.4 Hz	2.91, t, 6.8 Hz	2.67, t, 6.8 Hz	5.06, s	7.18–7.87, m, 3H		
2b	1.05, t, 7.4 Hz	2.48, q, 7.4 Hz	2.90, t, 6.8 Hz	2.71, t, 6.8 Hz	5.05, s	7.32–7.74, m, 3H		
3b	1.03, t, 7.4 Hz	2.46, q, 7.4 Hz	2.92, t, 6.8 Hz	2.68, t, 6.8 Hz	5.07, s	7.46–7.66, m, 3H		
4b	1.04, t, 7.4 Hz	2.50, q, 7.4 Hz	2.93, t, 6.8 Hz	2.69, t, 6.8 Hz	5.18, s	7.25–7.77, m, 3H		
5b	1.05, t, 7.4 Hz	2.50, q, 7.4 Hz	2.91, t, 6.8 Hz	2.68, t, 6.8 Hz	5.22, s	7.41–7.79, m, 3H		
6b	1.04, t, 7.4 Hz	2.49, q, 7.4 Hz	2.92, t, 6.8 Hz	2.69, t, 6.8 Hz	5.06, s	7.05–7.22, m, 3H		
7b	1.05, t, 7.4 Hz	2.51, q, 7.4 Hz	2.93, t, 6.8 Hz	2.68, t, 6.8 Hz	5.07, s	6.58–7.46, m, 3H		
8b	1.04, t, 7.4 Hz	2.51, q, 7.4 Hz	2.91, t, 6.8 Hz	2.70, t, 6.8 Hz	5.07, s	6.76–7.24, m, 3H		
9b	1.04, t, 7.4 Hz	2.49, q, 7.4 Hz	2.92, t, 6.8 Hz	2.71, t, 6.8 Hz	5.11, s	7.22–7.83, m, 3H		
10b	1.03, t, 7.4 Hz	2.42, q, 7.4 Hz	2.90, t, 6.8 Hz	2.68, t, 6.8 Hz	5.04, s	6.88–7.22, m, 3H	2.38, s, Me	2.38, s, Me
11b	1.03, t, 7.4 Hz	2.43, q, 7.4 Hz	2.92, t, 6.8 Hz	2.69, t, 6.8 Hz	5.05, s	6.98–7.19, m, 3H	2.39, s, Me	2.39, s, Me
12b	1.04, t, 7.4 Hz	2.37, q, 7.4 Hz	2.85, t, 6.8 Hz	2.66, t, 6.8 Hz	5.16, s	7.16–7.42, m, 4H	2.49, s	
13b	1.05, t, 7.4 Hz	2.41, q, 7.4 Hz	2.86, t, 6.8 Hz	2.67, t, 6.8 Hz	5.22, s	7.15–7.54, m, 4H	2.44, s	
14b	1.05, t, 7.4 Hz	2.42, q, 7.4 Hz	2.88, t, 6.8 Hz	2.69, t, 6.8 Hz	5.21, s	7.13–7.45, m, 4H	2.45, s	
15b	1.05, t, 7.4 Hz	2.43, q, 7.4 Hz	2.87, t, 6.8 Hz	2.66, t, 6.8 Hz	5.23, s	6.82–7.25, m, 4H	11.2 br, s	
16b	1.04, t, 7.4 Hz	2.45, q, 7.4 Hz	2.89, t, 6.8 Hz	2.67, t, 6.8 Hz	5.18, s	6.79–7.28, m, 4H	11.5 br, s	
17b	1.05, t, 7.4 Hz	2.51, q, 7.4 Hz	2.91, t, 6.8 Hz	2.69, t, 6.8 Hz	5.18, s	6.72–7.02, m, 4H	11.3 br, s	
18b	1.04, t, 7.4 Hz	2.49, q, 7.4 Hz	2.88, t, 6.8 Hz	2.68, t, 6.8 Hz	5.05, s	6.68–7.18, m, 4H	11.6 br, s	
19b	1.05, t, 7.4 Hz	2.48, q, 7.4 Hz	2.89, t, 6.8 Hz	2.70, t, 6.8 Hz	5.22, s	6.65–7.23, m, 4H	11.8 br, s	
20b	1.04, t, 7.4 Hz	2.44, q, 7.4 Hz	2.88, t, 6.8 Hz	2.69, t, 6.8 Hz	5.19, s	6.64–7.22, m, 4H	11.7 br, s	

Table 4. ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl_3 , δ) of **1b-20b**

Compd.	6	5	4	3	2	1	1''	1'	2'	3'	4'	5'	6'	R	R'
1b	7.8	36.3	209.4	32.3	29.1	171.8	62.9	137.5	131.2	129.3	133.6	126.8	128.6		
2b	7.7	36.1	209.1	32.4	29.5	172.2	61.9	138.5	127.4	129.6	128.3	131.7	128.9		
3b	7.7	36.3	209.1	32.4	29.0	171.8	57.9	139.8	134.3	128.5	126.8	128.5	134.3		
4b	7.8	36.4	208.6	32.1	29.2	172.1	66.3	137.2	129.4	133.5	133.6	131.6	128.4		
5b	7.8	36.1	208.2	32.4	29.4	172.3	65.9	145.8	126.4	136.8	127.9	136.8	126.4		
6b	7.8	36.2	209.3	32.6	29.5	172.4	62.3	130.2	136.3	150.2	117.5	127.4	125.5		
7b	7.8	36.7	208.8	31.9	29.1	172.1	62.1	122.4	159.8	105.4	158.4	112.3	129.6		
8b	7.8	36.3	209.1	31.2	29.2	172.6	61.9	127.5	153.2	116.4	114.2	156.3	114.8		
9b	7.7	36.4	208.9	33.3	29.4	172.2	55.2	113.4	162.4	112.6	129.7	112.6	162.4		
10b	7.8	36.5	208.4	33.2	29.1	172.3	66.2	140.2	138.1	132.5	137.6	127.2	127.8	20.5,	22.6
11b	7.7	37.1	209.4	32.8	30.1	172.4	66.3	141.5	132.2	131.6	128.5	138.4	127.8	19.8,	22.4
12b	7.6	36.2	209.1	32.3	29.4	170.2	66.3	144.2	135.8	128.4	128.7	126.2	129.4	19.9	
13b	7.8	36.4	209.1	32.2	29.4	170.3	67.1	137.1	128.4	136.8	129.3	127.2	125.5	22.6	
14b	7.6	36.3	208.6	31.6	29.3	171.2	66.9	135.8	126.5	128.8	138.6	128.8	126.5	22.2	
15b	7.7	37.1	209.2	31.4	29.1	171.4	62.2	129.3	155.8	117.1	128.3	125.4	131.2		
16b	7.8	36.9	208.8	31.3	29.2	171.5	66.2	138.4	111.9	156.6	113.5	129.7	118.8		
17b	7.8	36.4	208.7	31.5	29.5	171.6	66.7	129.5	130.4	117.6	154.5	117.6	130.4		
17b	7.7	36.7	208.5	31.2	29.6	171.4	63.6	141.3	143.7	115.8	127.2	123.4	124.8		
19b	7.8	36.5	208.4	31.7	29.1	172.2	66.8	136.2	115.2	127.4	112.1	146.9	113.8		
20b	7.6	36.2	209.3	32.3	29.4	172.3	66.7	125.2	127.4	116.2	145.6	116.2	127.4		

2,4-Dichlorobenzyl 4-chloro-4-ketobutanoate (1a) :

Yield 65%, 1.53 g (5.2 mmol), viscous oil; MS, m/z ($I_r/\%$) : 295.54 (25) (M^+); UV-Vis (EtOH) λ_{max} nm (log ϵ) : 257.9 (3.7); FT-IR (Neat) ν_{max} (cm^{-1}) : 3086 (Ar-H), 1721 (C=O), 1777 (Cl-C=O), 1610, 1478 (C=C), 1262, 1144, 1021 (C-O), 720 (C-Cl); 1H and ^{13}C NMR (300 MHz, 75 MHz, $CDCl_3$) : (Tables 1 and 2); Analysis Calcd. for $C_{11}H_9Cl_3O_3$ (295.55) : C, 44.70; H, 3.07; Cl, 35.99; Found : C, 44.68; H, 3.11; Cl, 35.88%.

2,5-Dichlorobenzyl 4-chloro-4-ketobutanoate (2a) :

Yield 66%, 1.56 g (5.28 mmol), viscous oil; MS, m/z ($I_r/\%$) : 295.54 (22) (M^+); UV-Vis (EtOH) λ_{max} nm (log ϵ) : 262.5 (3.5); FT-IR (Neat) ν_{max} (cm^{-1}) : 3087 (Ar-H), 1724 (C=O), 1776 (Cl-C=O), 1609, 1433 (C=C), 1266, 1138, 1027 (C-O), 721 (C-Cl); 1H and ^{13}C NMR (300 MHz, 75 MHz, $CDCl_3$) : (Tables 1 and 2); Analysis Calcd. for $C_{11}H_9Cl_3O_3$ (295.55) : C, 44.70; H, 3.07; Cl, 35.99; Found : C, 44.69; H, 3.03; Cl, 35.89%.

2,6-Dichlorobenzyl 4-chloro-4-ketobutanoate (3a) :

Yield 64%, 1.51 g (5.12 mmol), viscous oil; MS, m/z ($I_r/\%$) : 295.55 (27) (M^+); UV-Vis (EtOH) λ_{max} nm (log ϵ) : 265.4 (3.9); FT-IR (Neat) ν_{max} (cm^{-1}) : 3083 (Ar-H), 1778 (Cl-C=O), 1727 (C=O), 1607, 1442 (C=C), 1248, 1121, 1011 (C-O), 726 (C-Cl); 1H and ^{13}C NMR (300 MHz, 75 MHz, $CDCl_3$) : (Tables 1 and 2); Analysis Calcd. for $C_{11}H_9Cl_3O_3$ (295.55) : C, 44.70; H, 3.07; Cl, 35.99; Found : C, 44.68; H, 3.02; Cl, 35.91%.

3,4-Dichlorobenzyl 4-chloro-4-ketobutanoate (4a) :

Yield 67%, 1.58 g (5.36 mmol), viscous oil; MS, m/z ($I_r/\%$) : 295.54 (21) (M^+); UV-Vis (EtOH) λ_{max} nm (log ϵ) : 254.5 (3.7); FT-IR (Neat) ν_{max} (cm^{-1}) : 3066 (Ar-H), 1777 (Cl-C=O), 1726 (C=O), 1611, 1444 (C=C), 1255, 1132, 1029 (C-O), 724 (C-Cl); 1H and ^{13}C NMR (300 MHz, 75 MHz, $CDCl_3$) : (Tables 1 and 2); Analysis Calcd. for $C_{11}H_9Cl_3O_3$ (295.55) : C, 44.70; H, 3.07; Cl, 35.99; Found : C, 44.67; H, 3.09; Cl, 35.92%.

3,5-Dichlorobenzyl 4-chloro-4-ketobutanoate (5a) :

Yield 67%, 1.58 g (5.36 mmol), viscous oil; MS, m/z ($I_r/\%$) : 295.56 (24) (M^+); UV-Vis (EtOH) λ_{max} nm (log ϵ) : 266.4 (3.9); FT-IR (Neat) ν_{max} (cm^{-1}) : 3095 (Ar-H), 1765 (Cl-C=O), 1722 (C=O), 1608, 1444 (C=C), 1248, 1129, 1022 (C-O), 727 (C-Cl); 1H and ^{13}C NMR (300 MHz, 75 MHz, $CDCl_3$) : (Tables 1 and 2); Analysis Calcd. for $C_{11}H_9Cl_3O_3$ (295.55) : C, 44.70; H, 3.07; Cl, 35.99; Found : C, 44.71; H, 3.05; Cl, 35.93%.

2,3-Difluorobenzyl 4-chloro-4-ketobutanoate (6a) :

Yield 68%, 1.43 g (5.44 mmol), viscous oil; MS, m/z ($I_r/\%$) : 262.75 (22) (M^+); UV-Vis (EtOH) λ_{max} nm (log ϵ) : 258.5 (4.2); FT-IR (Neat) ν_{max} (cm^{-1}) : 3088 (Ar-H), 1776 (Cl-C=O), 1728 (C=O), 1606, 1478 (C=C), 1252, 1126, 1010 (C-O), 1150 (C-F); 1H and ^{13}C NMR (300 MHz, 75 MHz, $CDCl_3$) : (Tables 1 and 2); Analysis Calcd. for $C_{11}H_9ClF_2O_3$ (262.64) : C, 50.30; H, 3.45; Cl, 13.50; F, 14.47; Found : C, 50.28; H, 3.47; Cl, 13.52; F, 14.44%.

2,4-Difluorobenzyl 4-chloro-4-ketobutanoate (7a) :

Yield 68%, 1.43 g (5.44 mmol), viscous oil; MS, m/z ($I_r/\%$) : 262.66 (22) (M^+); UV-Vis (EtOH) λ_{max} nm (log ϵ) : 263.2 (4.0); FT-IR (Neat) ν_{max} (cm^{-1}) : 3098 (Ar-H), 1766 (Cl-C=O), 1729 (C=O), 1594, 1476 (C=C), 1239, 1119, 1026 (C-O), 1151 (C-F); 1H and ^{13}C NMR (300 MHz, 75 MHz, $CDCl_3$) : (Tables 1 and 2); Analysis Calcd. for $C_{11}H_9ClF_2O_3$ (262.64) : C, 50.30; H, 3.45; Cl, 13.50; F, 14.47; Found : C, 50.29; H, 3.46; Cl, 13.49; F, 14.46%.

2,5-Difluorobenzyl 4-chloro-4-ketobutanoate (8a) :

Yield 71%, 1.49 g (5.68 mmol), viscous oil; MS, m/z ($I_r/\%$) : 262.63 (22) (M^+); UV-Vis (EtOH) λ_{max} nm (log ϵ) : 258.4 (3.5); FT-IR (Neat) ν_{max} (cm^{-1}) : 3099 (Ar-H), 1767 (Cl-C=O), 1727 (C=O), 1599, 1486 (C=C), 1258, 1122, 1025 (C-O), 1153 (C-F); 1H and ^{13}C NMR (300 MHz, 75 MHz, $CDCl_3$) : (Tables 1 and 2); Analysis Calcd. for

$C_{11}H_9ClF_2O_3$ (262.64) : C, 50.30; H, 3.45; Cl, 13.50; F, 14.47; Found : C, 50.28; H, 3.47; Cl, 13.48; F, 14.49%.

2,6-Difluorobenzyl 4-chloro-4-ketobutanoate (9a) :

 Yield 64%, 1.34 g (5.12 mmol), viscous oil; MS, m/z ($I_r/\%$) : 262.64 (22) (M^+); UV-Vis (EtOH) λ_{max} nm (log ϵ) : 257.7 (3.9); FT-IR (Neat) ν_{max} (cm^{-1}) : 3088 (Ar-H), 1765 (Cl-C=O), 1726 (C=O), 1597, 1406 (C=C), 1245, 1120, 1008 (C-O), 1157 (C-F); 1H and ^{13}C NMR (300 MHz, $CDCl_3$) : (Tables 1 and 2); Analysis Calcd. for $C_{11}H_9ClF_2O_3$ (262.64) : C, 50.30; H, 3.45; Cl, 13.50; F, 14.47; Found : C, 50.31; H, 3.47; Cl, 13.49; F, 14.46%.

2,4-Dimethylbenzyl 4-chloro-4-ketobutanoate (10a) :

 Yield 68%, 1.38 g (5.44 mmol), viscous oil; MS, m/z ($I_r/\%$) : 254.69 (22) (M^+); UV-Vis (EtOH) λ_{max} nm (log ϵ) : 262.5 (3.5); FT-IR (Neat) ν_{max} (cm^{-1}) : 3097 (Ar-H), 1775 (Cl-C=O), 1731 (C=O), 1605, 1435 (C=C), 1254, 1123, 1008 (C-O); 1H and ^{13}C NMR (300 MHz, $CDCl_3$) : (Tables 1 and 2); Analysis Calcd. for $C_{13}H_{15}ClO_3$ (254.71) : C, 61.30; H, 5.94; Cl, 13.92; Found : C, 61.28; H, 5.95; Cl, 13.94%.

2,5-Dimethylbenzyl 4-chloro-4-ketobutanoate (11a) :

 Yield 69%, 1.40 g (5.52 mmol), viscous oil; MS, m/z ($I_r/\%$) : 254.70 (22) (M^+); UV-Vis (EtOH) λ_{max} nm (log ϵ) : 266.8 (3.8); FT-IR (Neat) ν_{max} (cm^{-1}) : 3088 (Ar-H), 1767 (Cl-C=O), 1722 (C=O), 1602, 1487 (C=C), 1244, 1136, 1012 (C-O); 1H and ^{13}C NMR (300 MHz, $CDCl_3$) : (Tables 1 and 2); Analysis Calcd. for $C_{13}H_{15}ClO_3$ (254.71) : C, 61.30; H, 5.94; Cl, 13.92; Found : C, 61.31; H, 5.98; Cl, 13.97%.

2-Methylbenzyl 4-chloro-4-ketobutanoate (12a) :

 Yield 76%, 1.82 g (6.16 mmol), viscous oil; MS, m/z ($I_r/\%$) : 240 (22) (M^+); UV-Vis (MeOH), λ_{max} nm (log ϵ) : 258.5 (3.64); FT-IR (Neat) ν_{max} (cm^{-1}) : 3083 (Ar-H), 1731

(C=O), 1779 (Cl-C=O), 1596, 1543, 1422 (C=C), 1243, 1122, 1020 (C-O); 1H and ^{13}C NMR (300 MHz, 75 MHz, $CDCl_3$) : (Tables 1 and 2); Analysis Calcd. for $C_{12}H_{13}ClO_3$ (240.68) : C, 59.88; H, 5.44; Cl, 14.73; Found : C, 59.67; H, 5.53; Cl, 14.78%.

3-Methylbenzyl 4-chloro-4-ketobutanoate (13a) :

 Yield 75%, 1.46 g (6.08 mmol), viscous oil; MS, m/z ($I_r/\%$) : 240.87 (22) (M^+); UV-Vis (EtOH), λ_{max} nm (log ϵ) : 259.9 (3.47); FT-IR (Neat) ν_{max} (cm^{-1}) : 3099 (Ar-H), 1732 (C=O), 1782 (Cl-C=O), 1599, 1556, 1435 (C=C, Ar-H), 1243, 1134, 1022 (C-O); 1H and ^{13}C NMR (300 MHz, 75 MHz, $CDCl_3$) : (Tables 1 and 2); Analysis Calcd. for $C_{12}H_{13}ClO_3$ (240.68) : C, 59.88; H, 5.44; Cl, 14.73; Found : C, 59.65; H, 5.59; Cl, 14.77%.

4-Methylbenzyl 4-chloro-4-ketobutanoate (14a) :

 Yield 77%, 1.50 g (6.24 mmol), viscous oil; MS, m/z ($I_r/\%$) : 240.67 (22) (M^+); UV-Vis (EtOH) λ_{max} nm (log ϵ) : 263.4 (3.68); FT-IR (Neat) ν_{max} (cm^{-1}) : 3076 (Ar-H), 1728 (C=O), 1786 (Cl-C=O), 1598, 1547, 1434 (C=C, Ar-H), 1243, 1132, 1022 (C-O); 1H and ^{13}C NMR (300 MHz, 75 MHz, $CDCl_3$) : (Tables 1 and 2); Analysis Calcd. for $C_{12}H_{13}ClO_3$ (240.68) : C, 59.88; H, 5.44; Cl, 14.73; Found : C, 59.78; H, 5.55; Cl, 14.71%.

2-Hydroxybenzyl 4-chloro-4-ketobutanoate (15a) :

 Yield 75%, 1.47 g (6.08 mmol), viscous oil; MS, m/z ($I_r/\%$) : 242.66 (23) (M^+); UV-Vis (EtOH) λ_{max} nm (log ϵ) : 257.8 (3.63); FT-IR (Neat) ν_{max} (cm^{-1}) : 3365-3122 (OH), 3076 (Ar-H), 1745 (C=O), 1791 (Cl-C=O), 1599, 1538, 1443 (C=C, Ar-H), 1240, 1133 (C-O); 1H and ^{13}C NMR (300 MHz, 75 MHz, $CDCl_3$) : (Tables 1 and 2); Analysis Calcd. for $C_{11}H_{11}ClO_4$ (242.65) : C, 54.45; H, 4.57; Cl, 14.61; Found : C, 54.57; H, 4.66; Cl, 14.55%.

3-Hydroxybenzyl 4-chloro-4-ketobutanoate (16a) :

 Yield 76%, 1.49 g (6.16 mmol), viscous oil; MS, m/z ($I_r/\%$) : 242.64 (23) (M^+); UV-Vis

(EtOH) $\lambda_{\max}$ nm (log ϵ) : 259.5 (3.45); FT-IR (Neat) $\nu_{\max}$ (cm^{-1}) : 3376–3118 (OH), 3096 (Ar-H), 1738 (C=O), 1783 (CO-Cl), 1618, 1554, 1448, (C=C, Ar-H), 1242, 1134, 1041 (C-O); ^1H and ^{13}C NMR (300 MHz, 75 MHz, CDCl_3) : (Tables 1 and 2); Analysis Calcd. for $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{11}\text{ClO}_4$ (242.65) : C, 54.45; H, 4.57; Cl, 14.61; Found : C, 54.56; H, 4.64; Cl, 14.56%.

4-Hydroxybenzyl 4-chloro-4-ketobutanoate (17a) :

Yield 77%, 1.51 g (6.24 mmol), viscous oil; MS, m/z ($I_r/\%$) : 242.64 (23) (M^+);

UV-Vis (EtOH) $\lambda_{\max}$ nm (log ϵ) : 256.7 (3.72); FT-IR (Neat) $\nu_{\max}$ (cm^{-1}) : 3355–3120 (OH), 3078 (Ar-H), 1748 (C=O), 1781 (Cl-C=O), 1614, 1545, 1446 (C=C, Ar-H), 1224, 1133, 1040 (C-O); ^1H and ^{13}C NMR (300 MHz, 75 MHz, CDCl_3) : (Tables 1 and 2); Analysis Calcd. for $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{11}\text{ClO}_4$ (242.65) : C, 54.45; H, 4.57; Cl, 14.61; Found : C, 54.59; H, 4.67; Cl, 14.63%.

2-Aminobenzyl 4-chloro-4-ketobutanoate (18a) :

Yield 72%, 1.41 g (5.84 mmol), viscous oil; MS, m/z ($I_r/\%$) : 241.66 (21) (M^+); UV-Vis (EtOH) $\lambda_{\max}$ nm (log ϵ) : 257.8

(3.92); FT-IR (Neat) $\nu_{\max}$ (cm^{-1}) : 3215 (NH_2), 3088 (Ar-H), 1742 (C=O), 1788 (Cl-C=O), 1607, 1532, 1499, 1458, (C=C, Ar-H), 1384 (C-N), 1257, 1231, 1130, 1202, 1098, 1042, 1012 (C-O); ^1H and ^{13}C NMR (300 MHz, 75 MHz, CDCl_3) : (Tables 1 and 2); Analysis Calcd. for $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{12}\text{ClNO}_3$ (241.67) : C, 54.67; H, 5.00; Cl, 14.67; N, 5.80; Found : C, 54.64; H, 4.92; Cl, 14.68; N, 5.78%.

3-Aminobenzyl 4-chloro-4-ketobutanoate (19a) :

Yield 71%, 1.39 g (5.76 mmol), viscous oil; MS, m/z ($I_r/\%$) : 241.66 (21) (M^+); UV-Vis (EtOH) $\lambda_{\max}$ nm (log ϵ) : 258.7

(3.76); FT-IR (Neat) $\nu_{\max}$ (cm^{-1}) : 3215 (Broad, NH_2), 3097 (Ar-H), 1738 (C=O), 1787 (Cl-C=O), 1592, 1520, 1442 (C=C, Ar-H), 1391 (C-N), 1246, 1135, 1045 (C-O); ^1H and ^{13}C NMR (300 MHz, 75 MHz, CDCl_3) : (Tables 1 and 2); Analysis Calcd. for $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{12}\text{ClNO}_3$ (241.67) : C, 54.67; H, 5.00;

Cl, 14.67; N, 5.80; Found : C, 54.65; H, 4.91; Cl 14.69; N, 5.77%.

4-Aminobenzyl 4-chloro-4-ketobutanoate (20a) :

Yield 78%, 1.53 g (6.32 mmol), viscous oil; MS, m/z ($I_r/\%$) : 241.68 (24) (M^+);

UV-Vis (EtOH) $\lambda_{\max}$ nm (log ϵ) : 256.2 (3.6); FT-IR (Neat) $\nu_{\max}$ (cm^{-1}) : 3232 (Broad, intense, NH_2), 3085 (Ar-H), 1739 (C=O), 1779 (Cl-C=O), 1607, 1592, 1458 (C=C, Ar-H), 1382 (C-N), 1263, 1154, 1020 (C-O); ^1H and ^{13}C NMR (300 MHz, 75 MHz, CDCl_3) : (Tables 1 and 2); Analysis Calcd. for $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{12}\text{ClNO}_3$ (241.67) : C, 54.67; H, 5.00; Cl, 14.67; N, 5.80; Found : C, 54.65; H, 4.91; Cl, 14.69; N, 5.77%.

2,4-Dichlorobenzyl γ -ketoheptanoate (1b) :

Yield 72%, 1.04 g (3.60 mmol), viscous oil; MS, m/z ($I_r/\%$) : 289.15 (33) (M^+); UV-

Vis (EtOH) $\lambda_{\max}$ nm (log ϵ) : 258.5 (3.72); FT-IR (Neat) $\nu_{\max}$ (cm^{-1}) : 3076 (Ar-H), 1728 (CO_2Ar), 1767 (C=O), 1615, 1479 (C=C), 1267, 1148, 1023 (C-O), 722 (C-Cl); ^1H and ^{13}C NMR (300 MHz, 75 MHz, CDCl_3) : (Tables 3 and 4); Analysis Calcd. for $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{14}\text{Cl}_2\text{O}_3$ (289.15) : C, 54.00; H, 4.88; Cl, 24.52; Found : C, 54.05; H, 4.89; Cl, 24.51%.

2,5-Dichlorobenzyl γ -ketoheptanoate (2b) :

Yield 75%, 1.08 g (3.75 mmol), viscous oil; MS, m/z ($I_r/\%$) : 289.15 (31) (M^+); UV-Vis (EtOH) $\lambda_{\max}$ nm (log ϵ) : 264.2

(3.57); FT-IR (Neat) $\nu_{\max}$ (cm^{-1}) : 3097 (Ar-H), 1726 (CO_2Ar), 1768 (C=O), 1619, 1439 (C=C), 1268, 1131, 1024 (C-O), 725 (C-Cl); ^1H and ^{13}C NMR (300 MHz, 75 MHz, CDCl_3) : (Tables 3 and 4); Analysis Calcd. for $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{14}\text{Cl}_2\text{O}_3$ (289.15) : C, 54.00; H, 4.88; Cl, 24.52; Found : C, 54.09; H, 4.87; Cl, 24.53%.

2,6-Dichlorobenzyl γ -ketoheptanoate (3b) :

Yield 76%, 1.10 g (3.80 mmol), viscous oil; MS, m/z ($I_r/\%$) : 289.15 (34) (M^+); UV-Vis (EtOH) $\lambda_{\max}$ nm (log ϵ) : 264.2

(3.57); FT-IR (Neat) $\nu_{\max}$ (cm^{-1}) : 3099 (Ar-H), 1729 (CO_2Ar), 1764 (C=O), 1622, 1428 (C=C), 1262, 1135,

1020 (C-O), 725 (C-Cl); ¹H and ¹³C NMR (300 MHz, 75 MHz, CDCl₃) : (Tables 3 and 4); Analysis Calcd. for C₁₃H₁₄Cl₂O₃ (289.15) : C, 54.00; H, 4.88; Cl, 24.52; Found : C, 54.10; H, 4.85; Cl, 24.51%.

3,4-Dichlorobenzyl γ-ketohexanoate (4b) :

 Yield 77%, 1.11 g (3.85 mmol), viscous oil; MS, *m/z* (*I_r*%) : 289.15 (30) (M⁺); UV-Vis (EtOH) λ_{max} nm (log ε) : 258.4 (3.88); FT-IR (Neat) ν_{max} (cm⁻¹) : 3087 (Ar-H), 1759 (C=O), 1728 (CO₂Ar), 1619, 1447 (C=C), 1258, 1135, 1028 (C-O), 727 (C-Cl); ¹H and ¹³C NMR (300 MHz, 75 MHz, CDCl₃) : (Tables 3 and 4); Analysis Calcd. for C₁₃H₁₄Cl₂O₃ (289.15) : C, 54.00; H, 4.88; Cl, 24.52; Found : C, 54.08; H, 4.89; Cl, 24.53%.

3,5-Dichlorobenzyl γ-ketohexanoate (5b) :

 Yield 76%, 1.10 g (3.80 mmol), viscous oil; MS, *m/z* (*I_r*%) : 289.15 (29) (M⁺); UV-Vis (EtOH) λ_{max} nm (log ε) : 266.6 (3.79); FT-IR (Neat) ν_{max} (cm⁻¹) : 3066 (Ar-H), 1767 (C=O), 1725 (CO₂Ar), 1618, 1438 (C=C), 1249, 1127, 1020 (C-O), 732 (C-Cl); ¹H and ¹³C NMR (300 MHz, 75 MHz, CDCl₃) : (Tables 3 and 4); Analysis Calcd. for C₁₃H₁₄Cl₂O₃ (289.15) : C, 54.00; H, 4.88; Cl, 24.52; Found : C, 54.07; H, 4.87; Cl, 24.51%.

2,3-Difluorobenzyl γ-ketohexanoate (6b) :

 Yield 71%, 0.91 g (3.55 mmol), viscous oil; MS, *m/z* (*I_r*%) : 256.25 (28) (M⁺); UV-Vis (EtOH) λ_{max} nm (log ε) : 264.6 (4.25); FT-IR (Neat) ν_{max} (cm⁻¹) : 3076 (Ar-H), 1765 (C=O), 1729 (CO₂Ar), 1608, 1483 (C=C), 1258, 1128, 1015 (C-O), 1155 (C-F); ¹H and ¹³C NMR (300 MHz, 75 MHz, CDCl₃) : (Tables 3 and 4); Analysis Calcd. for C₁₃H₁₄F₂O₃ (256.25) : C, 60.93; H, 5.51; F, 14.83; Found : C, 60.92; H, 5.52; F, 14.82%.

2,4-Difluorobenzyl γ-ketohexanoate (7b) :

 Yield 69%, 0.88 g (3.45 mmol), viscous oil; MS, *m/z* (*I_r*%) : 256.25 (26) (M⁺); UV-Vis (EtOH) λ_{max} nm (log ε) : 265.3 (3.98); FT-IR (Neat) ν_{max} (cm⁻¹) : 3094 (Ar-H),

1767 (C=O), 1731 (CO₂Ar), 1597, 1471 (C=C), 1245, 1114, 1021 (C-O), 1158 (C-F); ¹H and ¹³C NMR (300 MHz, 75 MHz, CDCl₃) : (Tables 3 and 4); Analysis Calcd. for C₁₃H₁₄F₂O₃ (256.25) : C, 60.93; H, 5.51; F, 14.83; Found : C, 60.94; H, 5.50; F, 14.84%.

2,5-Difluorobenzyl γ-ketohexanoate (8b) :

 Yield 72%, 0.92 g (3.60 mmol), viscous oil; MS, *m/z* (*I_r*%) : 256.25 (33) (M⁺); UV-Vis (EtOH) ε_{max} nm (log ε) : 265.8 (3.57); FT-IR (Neat) ν_{max} (cm⁻¹) : 3092 (Ar-H), 1768 (C=O), 1728 (CO₂Ar), 1594, 1489 (C=C), 1250, 1130, 1026 (C-O), 1149 (C-F); ¹H and ¹³C NMR (300 MHz, 75 MHz, CDCl₃) : (Tables 3 and 4); Analysis Calcd. for C₁₃H₁₄F₂O₃ (256.25) : C, 60.93; H, 5.51; F, 14.83; Found : C, 60.95; H, 5.52; F, 14.82%.

2,6-Difluorobenzyl γ-ketohexanoate (9b) :

 Yield 68%, 0.87 g (3.40 mmol), viscous oil; MS, *m/z* (*I_r*%) : 256.25 (34) (M⁺); UV-Vis (EtOH) λ_{max} nm (log ε) : 267.6 (3.95); FT-IR (Neat) ν_{max} (cm⁻¹) : 3075 (Ar-H), 1766 (C=O), 1732 (CO₂Ar), 1598, 1405 (C=C), 1235, 1129, 1011 (C-O), 1159 (C-F); ¹H and ¹³C NMR (300 MHz, 75 MHz, CDCl₃) : (Tables 3 and 4); Analysis Calcd. for C₁₃H₁₄F₂O₃ (256.25) : C, 60.93; H, 5.51; F, 14.83; Found : C, 60.94; H, 5.53; F, 14.85%.

2,4-Dimethylbenzyl γ-ketohexanoate (10b) :

 Yield 74%, 0.92 g (3.70 mmol), viscous oil; MS, *m/z* (*I_r*%) : 248.32 (27) (M⁺); UV-Vis (EtOH) λ_{max} nm (log ε) : 264.2 (3.56); FT-IR (Neat) ν_{max} (cm⁻¹) : 3094 (Ar-H), 1772 (C=O), 1731 (CO₂Ar), 1609, 1437 (C=C), 1259, 1122, 1018 (C-O); ¹H and ¹³C NMR (300 MHz, 75 MHz, CDCl₃) : (Tables 3 and 4); Analysis Calcd. for C₁₅H₂₀O₃ (248.32) : C, 72.55; H, 8.12; Found : C, 72.54; H, 8.13%.

2,5-Dimethylbenzyl γ-ketohexanoate (11b) :

 Yield 72%, 0.89 g (3.60 mmol), viscous oil; MS, *m/z* (*I_r*%) : 248.32 (24) (M⁺); UV-Vis (EtOH) λ_{max} nm (log ε) : 268.6

(3.78); FT-IR (Neat) $\nu_{\max}$ (cm^{-1}) : 3074 (Ar-H), 1765 (C=O), 1723 (CO_2Ar), 1607, 1485 (C=C), 1246, 1138, 1013 (C-O); ^1H and ^{13}C NMR (300 MHz, 75 MHz, CDCl_3) : (Tables 3 and 4); Analysis Calcd. for $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_3$ (248.32) : C, 72.55; H, 8.12; Found : C, 72.56; H, 8.11%.

2-Methylbenzyl γ -keto hexanoate (12b) :

 Yield 74%, 0.87 g (3.70 mmol), viscous oil; MS, m/z ($I_r/\%$) : 234.29 (28) (M^+); UV-Vis (MeOH), $\lambda_{\max}$ nm (log ϵ) : 272.1 (3.35); FT-IR (Neat) $\nu_{\max}$ (cm^{-1}) : 3084 (Ar-H), 1755 (C=O), 1719 (CO_2Ar), 1606, 1554, 1424 (C=C), 1228, 1120, 1025 (C-O); ^1H and ^{13}C NMR (300 MHz, 75 MHz, CDCl_3) : (Tables 3 and 4); Analysis Calcd. for $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_3$ (234.29) : C, 71.77; H, 7.74; Found : C, 71.73; H, 7.76%.

3-Methylbenzyl γ -keto hexanoate (13b) :

 Yield 73%, 0.86 g (3.65 mmol), viscous oil; MS, m/z ($I_r/\%$) : 234.29 (26) (M^+); UV-Vis (EtOH), $\lambda_{\max}$ nm (log ϵ) : 263.9 (3.66); FT-IR (Neat) $\nu_{\max}$ (cm^{-1}) : 3094 (Ar-H), 1735 (CO_2Ar), 1756 (C=O), 1622, 1550 1438 (C=C, Ar-H), 1255, 1136, 1028 (C-O); ^1H and ^{13}C NMR (300 MHz, 75 MHz, CDCl_3) : (Tables 3 and 4); Analysis Calcd. for $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_3$ (234.29) : C, 71.77; H, 7.74; Found : C, 71.75; H, 7.75%.

4-Methylbenzyl γ -keto hexanoate (14b) :

 Yield 77%, 0.90 g (3.85 mmol), viscous oil; MS, m/z ($I_r/\%$) : 234.29 (26) (M^+); UV-Vis (EtOH) $\lambda_{\max}$ nm (log ϵ) : 266.3 (3.64); FT-IR (Neat) $\nu_{\max}$ (cm^{-1}) : 3076 (Ar-H), 1731 (CO_2Ar), 1757 (C=O), 1596, 1557, 1444 (C=C, Ar-H), 1256, 1136, 1015 (C-O); ^1H and ^{13}C NMR (300 MHz, 75 MHz, CDCl_3) : (Tables 3 and 4); Analysis Calcd. for $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_3$ (234.29) : C, 71.77; H, 7.74; Found : C, 71.76; H, 7.74%.

2-Hydroxybenzyl γ -keto hexanoate (15b) :

 Yield 74%, 0.87 g (3.70 mmol), viscous oil; MS, m/z ($I_r/\%$) : 236.26 (23) (M^+); UV-Vis (EtOH) $\lambda_{\max}$ nm (log ϵ) : 259.7 (3.75); FT-IR (Neat) $\nu_{\max}$ (cm^{-1}) :

3225–3187 (OH), 3088 (Ar-H), 1739 (CO_2Ar), 1763 (C=O), 1608, 1532, 1440 (C=C, Ar-H), 1252, 1123 (C-O); ^1H and ^{13}C NMR (300 MHz, 75 MHz, CDCl_3) : (Tables 3 and 4); Analysis Calcd. for $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_4$ (236.26) : C, 66.09; H, 6.83; Found : C, 66.12; H, 6.84%.

3-Hydroxybenzyl γ -keto hexanoate (16b) :

 Yield 71%, 0.84 g (3.55 mmol), viscous oil; MS, m/z ($I_r/\%$) : 236.26 (23) (M^+); UV-Vis (EtOH) $\lambda_{\max}$ nm (log ϵ) : 263.6 (3.48); FT-IR (Neat) $\nu_{\max}$ (cm^{-1}) : 3276–3145 (OH), 3098 (Ar-H), 1736 (CO_2Ar), 1768 (C=O), 1619, 1551, 1442, (C=C, Ar-H), 1247, 1138, 1044 (C-O); ^1H and ^{13}C NMR (300 MHz, 75 MHz, CDCl_3) : (Tables 3 and 4); Analysis Calcd. for $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_4$ (236.26) : C, 66.09; H, 6.83; Found : C, 66.10; H, 6.82%.

4-Hydroxybenzyl γ -keto hexanoate (17b) :

 Yield 76%, 0.90 g (3.80 mmol), viscous oil; MS, m/z ($I_r/\%$) : 236.26 (21) (M^+); UV-Vis (EtOH) $\lambda_{\max}$ nm (log ϵ) : 259.4 (3.76); FT-IR (Neat) $\nu_{\max}$ (cm^{-1}) : 3255–3120 (OH), 3095 (Ar-H), 1749 (CO_2Ar), 1757 (C=O), 1617, 1546, 1443 (C=C, Ar-H), 1229, 1130, 1044 (C-O); ^1H and ^{13}C NMR (300 MHz, 75 MHz, CDCl_3) : (Tables 3 and 4); Analysis Calcd. for $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_4$ (236.26) : C, 66.09; H, 6.83; Found : C, 66.08; H, 6.85%.

2-Aminobenzyl γ -keto hexanoate (18b) :

 Yield 73%, 0.86 g (3.65 mmol), viscous oil; MS, m/z ($I_r/\%$) : 235.28 (24) (M^+); UV-Vis (EtOH) $\lambda_{\max}$ nm (log ϵ) : 262.9 (3.95); FT-IR (Neat) $\nu_{\max}$ (cm^{-1}) : 3235 (NH_2), 3089 (Ar-H), 1745 (CO_2Ar), 1764 (C=O), 1603, 1537, 1492, 1453 (C=C, Ar-H), 1381 (C-N), 1252, 1230, 1135, 1041, 1002 (C-O); ^1H and ^{13}C NMR (300 MHz, 75 MHz, CDCl_3) : (Tables 3 and 4); Analysis Calcd. for $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{17}\text{NO}_3$ (235.28) : C, 66.36; H, 7.28; N, 5.95; Found : C, 66.38; H, 7.27; N, 5.94%.

3-Aminobenzyl γ -keto hexanoate (19b) :

 Yield 69%, 0.81 g (3.45 mmol), viscous oil; MS, m/z ($I_r/\%$) : 235.28

(29) (M^+); UV-Vis (EtOH) $\lambda_{\max}$ nm (log ϵ): 264.2 (3.67); FT-IR (Neat) $\nu_{\max}$ (cm^{-1}): 3230 (Broad, NH_2), 3096 (Ar-H), 1739 (CO_2Ar), 1757 ($\text{C}=\text{O}$), 1598, 1533, 1456 ($\text{C}=\text{C}$, Ar-H), 1393 (C-N), 1241, 1136, 1042 (C-O); ^1H and ^{13}C NMR (300 MHz, 75 MHz, CDCl_3): (Tables 3 and 4); Analysis Calcd. for $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{17}\text{NO}_3$ (235.28): C, 66.36; H, 7.28; N, 5.95; Found: C, 66.34; H, 7.29; N, 5.96%.

4-Aminobenzyl γ -ketoheptanoate (20b) :

Yield 77%, 0.91 g (3.85 mmol), viscous oil; MS, m/z (I_r %) : 235.28 (25) (M^+); UV-Vis (EtOH) $\lambda_{\max}$

nm (log ϵ): 263.6 (3.64); FT-IR (Neat) $\nu_{\max}$ (cm^{-1}): 3236 (Broad, intense, NH_2), 3095 (Ar-H), 1738 (CO_2Ar), 1767 ($\text{C}=\text{O}$), 1611, 1595, 1459 ($\text{C}=\text{C}$, Ar-H), 1387 (C-N), 1268, 1153, 1026 (C-O); ^1H and ^{13}C NMR (300 MHz, 75 MHz, CDCl_3): (Tables 3 and 4). Analysis Calcd. for $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{17}\text{NO}_3$ (235.28): C, 66.36; H, 7.28; N, 5.95; Found: C, 66.35; H, 7.27; N, 5.97%.

Experimental

General experimental procedures :

All the required chemicals were of analytical grade, purchased from Merck (Germany) and used as received. The UV-Vis spectrum was recorded in absolute methanol on an Irmeco UV/Vis Model U-2020 spectrophotometer (Germany). IR spectra were obtained on a Tensor 27 FT-IR spectrophotometer supplied by Bruker (Germany). ^1H NMR (300 MHz) and ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz) (1D, 2D, homo/hetero-nuclear) spectra were procured in CDCl_3 on a Bruker Biospin, AMX 300 MHz FT NMR spectrometer (Bruker, Germany). EI-MS were acquired with a direct insertion probe on a double-focusing Finnigan MAT 112 at 70 eV. HR-EI-MS measurements were made on a JEOL HX 110 spectrometer (Jeol, Japan). Elemental analyses were performed by Midwest Microlab (USA). Column chromatography was carried out using silica gel (PF₂₅₄, mesh size 60–70; Merck, Germany), and thin layer chromatography was performed on pre-coated silica gel plates (20 × 20 cm, 0.2 mm thickness) with UV fluorescence (PF₂₅₄) (Merck, Germany).

General procedure for preparation of monoacids monochlorides (1a-20a) :

Acid chlorides (**1a-20a**) were prepared by following a standard procedure¹⁷. In brief, the required monoester (**1-20**; 8 mmol) and thionyl chloride (1.64 mL, 22.5 mmol) were mixed in a round-bottom reaction flask (100 mL) fitted with a reflux condenser. The mixture was heated to 30–40 °C for of 3–4 h and the excess of thionyl chloride was removed by heating at reduced pressure. The residue was subjected to open column chromatography on silica gel using a mixture of hexane/ethyl acetate ($\phi_r = 4 : 1 \rightarrow 1 : 4$) as an eluent to obtain pure compounds **1a-20a**.

Preparation of diethyl cadmium reagent :

The diethyl cadmium reagent was prepared from a freshly prepared Grignard solution by following a standard protocol¹⁷. Briefly, dry CdCl_2 (2.15 g, 11.8 mmol) was added to the Grignard reagent [prepared from ethyl bromide (1.06 g, 11.8 mmol) and magnesium metal (0.26 g, 11.8 mmol) cooled to 0 °C] and dry diethyl ether (60 mL) was added over a period of 10 min with vigorous stirring. Stirring was continued further for an hour and was used as freshly prepared.

General procedure for preparation of substituted benzyl γ -ketoesters (1b-20b) :

Gamma-ketoheptanoates (**1b-20b**) were prepared from acid chlorides (**1a-20a**), by following a standard methodology¹⁷. Briefly, 4-benzyloxy-4-ketobutanoyl chloride (5 mmol) was slowly added to the diethyl cadmium solution. After maintaining reflux for different lengths of time (Table 2), the mixture was allowed to stand overnight. The material was then poured into a beaker containing ice and aq. H_2SO_4 (1 M, 30 mL). The organic layer was extracted with diethyl ether (3 × 20 mL), washed with an aq. NaHCO_3 solution (20 mL) and dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 . After removal of the solvent, the obtained material was subjected to open column chromatography on silica gel and elution was made with the mixture of hexane/ethyl acetate ($\phi_r = 4 : 1 \rightarrow 1 : 4$) to get pure compounds (**1b-20b**).

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